

Agroecological Solutions for
Resilient Farming in West Africa

**Baseline Survey (WP2) - Women in Household (WiHH) Questionnaire
(Final Version)**

[\(Appendix H2 of CIRAWA_D2.2_Socio-Econ. and Env. Analysis_V.6.0_2024_06_29\)](#)

CIRAWA Project Information Leaflet

1. The Project is “CIRAWA – Agroecological Solutions for Resilient Farming in West Africa”. It is an European Commission Horizon 2020 funded research project with a main aim of unlocking the potential of agroecology practices in West Africa by building on existing indigenous and scientific knowledge to improve food and nutrition security, livelihoods and planetary health while tackling climate change and environmental impact of agricultural practices.
2. The research is being undertaken in four West African countries - Cape Verde, Ghana, Senegal and The Gambia - by 14 Partners from West Africa and Europe, with Fundacion CARTIF of Spain as Coordinator.
3. The research is strictly for development and academic purposes and will have no negative consequences on any person or group of persons. Part or all of the information given might be published in books, journals or other suitable academic outlets but will not be traced to anybody providing information.
4. Participation in the research is completely voluntary, and no negative consequences will arise from refusal to participate, or from withdrawing from participation if the need arises at any time during Project implementation.
5. Every person is advised to fully consider, with others if necessary, and prior to participation, any disadvantages, side effects, risks and/or discomforts that may arise from participation in the research before consenting to take part.
6. Unless specifically agreed otherwise, all information disclosed will be carefully made anonymous.
7. All information or data obtained will be held as confidential and will not be distributed to third parties other than through the normal process of information dissemination.
8. The Project has an internationally recognized professional as the Ethics Advisor, who is entirely independent of the research, and any dissatisfaction with any aspect of the conduct of the research may be referred to him/her.
9. **You are being asked to participate in the baseline survey of the Project.**

Do you consent to participate 1) Yes 2) No

Thank you!

A. QUESTIONNAIRE IDENTIFIERS

A1. Name of enumerator:

A2. Country A3. District/Province/County: A4. Name of Community:

A5. Date of interview:/...../..... (dd/mm/yyyy)

A6. Name of respondent: A7. Sex 1) Male 2) Female A8. Respondent's contact: Mobile

A9. Name of household head (HHH) (if different from A6) A10. Household ID

A11. Status of respondent: 1) Household head (HHH) 2) Spouse of HHH 3) Brother/Sister of HHH 4) Son/Daughter of HHH 5) Parent of HHH 6) Other (specify)

A12. Are you an indigene? 1) Yes 2) No

A13. How long have you been in this district? 1) < 5 years 2) 5-10 years 3) 11-20 years 4) > 20 years

A14. Location (GPS Coordinates) :/...../

C. CROP FARMING SYSTEMS (Own farms of all women in the HH)

C.1 Women Individual farms last (2022) production season and land characteristics

1.0 Women Farms	1.1 Crops/crop mixtures on plots last production season (Codes A)	1.2 Estimated area (in acres)	1.3 Inorganic fertilizer used? (1)Yes (2) No	1.4 Quantity used? (bags)	1.5 Organic manure used? (1)Yes (2) No	1.6 Method used for land preparation. (1) Hoe (2) Animal traction (3) Tractor (4) No till (5) Weedicides	1.1 Location 1) Compound farm 2) Bush farm	1.3 Distance from house (walking time)	1.4 Tenure (Codes B)	1.7 Soil fertility (Codes C)
1										
2										
3										
4										
5										
6										

Codes A (crops)

Cereals	Legumes	Roots and Tubers	Vegetable Crops	Other Crops
1. Millet	6. Groundnut	14. Yam	24. Leafy vegetables (local)	32. Kenaf
2. Sorghum	7. Bambara groundnut	15. Cassava	25. Leafy vegetables (exotic)	33. Cotton
3. Rice	8. Beans (Cowpea)	16. Sweet potato	26. Pepper	34. Tobacco
4. Maize	9. Neri	17. Frafra potato (Pesa)	27. Tomatoes	35. Mango
5. Other cereals (specify)	10. Soybeans	18. Potato (English/Irish)	28. Okro	36. Pawpaw/Papaye
	11. Pigeon pea	19. Carrots	29. Onions	37. Cashew
	12. Feijoca/Feijão Fava (phaseolus coccineus)	20. Turnip	30. Garden eggs	38. Moringa (Noni)
	13. Other legume (specify)	21. Beetroot	31. Other vegetables (specify)	39. Sesame
		22. Radish		40. Tigernuts
		23. Other roots and tubers (specify)		41. Sugarcane
				42. Coconut
				43. Banana
				44. Avocado (pear)
				45. Citrus (orange, lemon, guava, grapes)

				etc.) 46. Tamarin 47. Coffee 48. Bread fruit 49. Fig species 50. Others (specify)
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Examples of how to fill column 2 of table above:

6 means sole groundnut; 6/20/25 means Groundnuts/Tomatoes/Kenaf; 1/2/21 means millet/sorghum/okro.

* **There is need to verify what is being called an acre/hectare.**

Codes B: 1) Inheritance; 2) Leased; 3) Rented; 4) Borrowed (Free); 5) Share cropping; 6) Others (specify)	Codes C: 1) Very fertile , does not require manure or external inputs; 2) Fertile but requires limited external inputs and manure; 3) Average , requires external inputs or manure every year; 4) Poor , cannot produce anything without manure and/or external inputs; 5) Other
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1.8 How long have you been engaged in crop farming? years

C.2 Crop Production Constraints

2.0 What are your **FIVE** major constraints in crop production? (Rank 1-5 most severe to least severe)

Cons- traints	2.1 Soil fertility	2.2 Erratic rainfall	2.3 Land owner -ship	2.4 Access to farming land	2.5 Small farm size	2.6 Access to production inputs	2.7 Access to extension services	2.8 Pests and diseases	2.9 Erosion	2.10 Access to weather information	2.11 Finance	2.12 Labour	2.13 Weeds	2.14 Other (Specify)
Ranks (1 to 5)														

2.15 Are there any fields where crops do not respond to application of inorganic fertilizers? **1) Yes 2) No**

2.16 If yes, indicate the farm plots (in C1) that are so? (Farm plot 1 to Farm plot 10)

2.17. What is the main land/soil problems you encounter?

1) Flooding 2) Acidity/alkalinity 3) Salinity 4) Loss of fertility 5) Soil compaction 6) Poor soil structure 7) Others (specify)

2.18 What are the main soil improvement practices that you undertake?

1) Crop rotation 2) Shifting cultivation 3) Use of manure (organic materials) 4) Use of fertilizer 5) Mixed cropping 6) Land fallow
7) Others (specify)

2.19 Which are your main sources of finance for your livelihood activities?

1) Commercial banks 2) Community and/or rural banks 3) Microfinance institutions (susu groups, cooperatives, VSL etc) 4) Non-governmental Organizations
5) Friends and relatives 6) Self 7) Others (specify)

C.3 Planting materials and sources

	3.1 Type of seeds used	3.2 Planted in 2022 1) Yes 2) No	3.3 Planted always? 1) Yes 2) No	3.4 Main source of planting material: 1) own seed (farmer-saved-seed) 2) local seed (purchased) 3) Local seed (from other farmers) 3) Improved seed (purchased)	3.5 Special characteristic of the planting material (See Codes below - Multiple selection allowed)
Maize	Indigenous (local)				
	Improved (Open pollinated)				
	Improved, (Hybrid)				
Rice	Rice – Indigenous				
	Rice-Improved				
	Rice – Hybrid				
Sorghum	Indigenous				
	“Improved”				
Millet	Indigenous				
	“Improved”				
Groundnut	Indigenous				
	“Improved”				
Beans (Cowpea)	Indigenous				
	“Improved”				
Soybeans	Indigenous				
	“Improved”				
Feijoca/ Feijão fava	Indigenous				
	“Improved”				
Cassava	Indigenous				
	“Improved”				
Yam	Indigenous				
	“Improved”				
Sweet potato	Indigenous (local)				
	“Improved”				
Vegetables	Indigenous (local)				
	Exotic				
Onion	Indigenous (local)				

	“Improved”				
Potato	Indigenous (local)				
	“Improved”				
Other (specify)	Indigenous (local)				
	“Improved”				

Codes for Special Characteristics (Multiple selection allowed): 1) High yielding 2) Drought resistance/tolerant 3) Can withstand flooding/submergence tolerant 4) Pests resistant 5) High nutritive quality value 6) Good taste quality 7) Good storability 8) Easily available 9) Other (Specify)

D. OUTPUT AND INCOME FROM CROP FARMS (Own farms of women in the HH – 2020 season)

D.1 Women Farms by Plots

1.0 Plot	1.1 Crops (Use crop codes as in C1)*	1.2 Total quantity harvested (indicate units) (standard units will be provided)	1.3 Price per unit (local currency)	1.4 Value of output (local currency)**	1.5 Euro equivalent (of 1.4)**	1.6 Percentage quantity normally sold (%)	1.7 Estimated cash income obtained (from sale of crops/produce in 1.6) (local currency)**	1.8 Euro Equivalent (of 1.7)**	1.9 Percentage quantity normally left for home consumption (%)	1.10 Percentage quantity normally given out to relatives, friends etc. (%)
1										
2.										
3.										
4.										
5.										
6.										

*Choose the 2 main crops in the case of crop mixtures. **Will not be part of questionnaire but will be computed.

D.2 List five crops in order of importance to you and give reasons

2.0 Crop	2.1 Rank in order of importance to you (1= Most important)	2.2 Reason (s) for rank
Millet		
Sorghum		
Rice		
Maize		
Groundnut		
Beans (cowpea)		
Soybeans		
Feijoca/ Feijão fava		
Yam		
Cassava		
Sweet potato		
Potato (English/Irish)		
Carrots		
Tomato		
Onion		
Okro		
Cotton		
Other (specify)		
Other (specify)		

E. FARMING SYSTEMS: LIVESTOCK

E.1 Women ownership, sale and management

1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	1.9	1.10	1.11	1.12
Types of animal	Number owned by HH last year	Number sold by HH last year	Cash obtained from sales last year (local currency)	Euro equivalent (of 1.3)*	Number owned by HH this year	Number sold by HH this year	Cash obtained from sales this year (local currency)*	Euro equivalent (of 1.7)*	Who takes care of the livestock? (Codes A)	What are the arrangements with hired herdsmen? (Codes B)	Any supplementary feeding (1) Yes (2) No	Any vet. drugs and treatment (1) Yes (2) No
Cattle												
Bullocks (for ploughing)												
Donkeys												
Horse												
Sheep												
Goats												
Pigs												
Rabbits												
Guinea pigs												
Fowls (Chickens)												
Guinea fowls												
Ducks												
Others (specify)												

* Will not be part of questionnaire but will be computed.

Codes A: 1) Household members; 2) Hired herdsmen 3) Herdsmen (sedentary) 4) Pastoralists (nomads) 5) Other (specify)

Codes B: 1) Cash payment 2) In-kind payment 3) Cash and in-kind payment 4) Other (specify)

(State the nature of in-kind payments – Please record in notebooks)

1.13 What are your **THREE** major constraints in the different types of livestock production? Rank 1-3 most severe to least severe

Constraints	1.1 Lack of feed in dry season	1.2 Lack of water in dry season	1.3 Diseases	1.4 Theft	1.5 Poor housing	1.6 Lack of market	1.6 Access to information on livestock management	1.7 Access to vet services	1.8 Other (specify)
Cattle									
Bullocks (for ploughing)									
Donkeys									
Horses									
Sheep									
Goats									
Pigs									
Rabbits									
Guinea pigs									
Fowls (chickens)									
Guinea fowls									
Ducks									
Others (specify)									

Lack implies very inadequate.

E.2 Animal Breeds

	2.1 Type of seeds used/reared	2.2 Commonly reared 1) Yes 2) No	2.3 Rarely reared 1) Yes 2) No	2.4 Source of breed 1) own breed 2) local (purchased) 3) Local (given by other farmers) 3) Exotic (purchased)	2.5 Special characteristic of the breed (See Codes below)
Cattle	Indigenous (local)				
	Crossbred				
	Exotic				
Sheep	Indigenous				
	Crossbred				
	Exotic				
Goats	Indigenous				
	Crossbred				
	Exotic				
Pigs	Indigenous				
	Crossbred				
	Exotic				
Fowls (Chickens)	Indigenous				
	Crossbred				
	Exotic				
Guinea fowls	Indigenous				
	Crossbred				
	Exotic				
Other (specify)	Indigenous				
	Crossbred				
	Exotic				

Codes for special characteristics (Multiple selections allowed): 1) Highly productive (meat, milk, egg etc) 2) Hardy (resilient in environment) 3) Disease resistant 4) Good taste 5) Easily available 6) Produces a lot of manure 7) Other (Specify)

F. IRRIGATION

1.0 Do you or any member of your HH undertake irrigation or have a dry season garden/farm? 1) Yes 2) No

What type of irrigation do you undertake?

Irrigation type	1.1 Type undertake 1) Yes 2) No	1.2 What crops grown? (Use Codes A)	1.3 Types of soil amendments used. 1) Only inorganic fertilizers 2) Only organic fertilizers 3) Inorganic and organic fertilizers	1.4 Degree of success. 1) Very successful 2) Successful (OK) 3) Somehow successful (Comci comca) 4) Poor	1.5 Main constraints (use Codes B)
Smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – Bucket and jerry can fetch					
Smallholder surface water irrigation (using rivers and streams) – Diesel and petrol pumps					
Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Bucket and jerry can fetch					
Smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – Diesel and petrol pumps					
Drip irrigation systems (mechanized systems)					
Dams and canals systems – Gravity flow (small and medium size dams)					
Dams and canal systems – Gravity flow (large dams)					
Smallholder urban and peri-urban irrigation					
Backyard gardening (using waste water)					
Other (specify)					
Other (specify)					

Codes A (for crops): See below (next page)

Codes B (main constraints): 1) Poor access to irrigated land 2) Poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc) 3) High costs of inputs 4) Inadequate access to markets for sale of produce 5) Water shortages 6) Other (s) (specify)

Codes A (crops)

Cereals	Legumes	Roots and Tubers	Vegetable Crops	Other Crops
1. Millet	6. Groundnut	14. Yam	24. Leafy vegetables (local)	32. Kenaf
2. Sorghum	7. Bambara groundnut	15. Cassava	25. Leafy vegetables (exotic)	33. Cotton
3. Rice	8. Beans (Cowpea)	16. Sweet potato	26. Pepper	34. Tobacco
4. Maize	9. Neri	17. Frafra potato (Pesa)	27. Tomatoes	35. Mango
5. Other cereals (specify)	10. Soybeans	18. Potato (English/Irish)	28. Okro	36. Pawpaw/Papaye
	11. Pigeon pea	19. Carrots	29. Onions	37. Cashew
	12. Feijoca/Feijão Fava (phaseolus coccineus)	20. Turnip	30. Garden eggs	38. Moringa (Noni)
	13. Other legume (specify)	21. Beetroot	31. Other vegetables (specify)	39. Sesame
		22. Radish		40. Tigernuts
		23. Other roots and tubers (specify)		41. Sugarcane
				42. Coconut
				43. Banana
				44. Avocado (pear)
				45. Citrus (orange, lemon, guava, grapes etc.)
				46. Tamarin
				47. Coffee
				48. Bread fruit
				49. Fig species
				50. Others (specify)

1.6 Which of the above crops do you or any member of your household cultivate as cash crops? (Cash crop is any crop cultivated mainly (over 75%) for sale).

G. HHs OTHER SOURCES OF INCOME IN THE PAST ONE YEAR

1.0 Source	1.1 Rank most important 1-5; 1 being the most important item)	1.2 Estimated amount (Local currency)	1.3Euro equivalent
1. Sale of labour			
2. Remittances			
3. Gifts			
4. Sale of firewood			
5. Charcoal production			
6. Illegal/small scale mining			
7. Sale of fruits (shea, dawadawa etc)			
8. Petty trading/food vending			
9. Food processing			
10. Salary			
11. Transportation services (carrying manures, harvested crops, people as a service)			
12. Other (specify)			
13. Other (specify)			

1.4 What can you do to increase your income?

.....

H. EXPENDITURE IN THE PAST ONE YEAR

1.0 Expenditure Items	1.1 Rank most important 1-5 . 1 being the most important item)	1.2 Give estimate of how much is spent on item in the past one year (in local currency)	1.3 Euro equivalent (of 1.2)
1. Food (grain)			
2. Soup ingredients			
3. Meat and dairy			
4. Farm inputs			
5. Livestock inputs			
6. Labour/Animal traction/tractor hire			
7. Irrigation water charges			
8. Transportation (for farm activities)			
9. Transportation (general)			
10. Orthodox health care for HH members			
11. Traditional health care for HH members			
12. Schooling expenses			
13. Clothing			
14. Church & other religious contributions			
15. Sacrifices			
16. Funerals and other social activities			
17. Remittances/Gifts			
18. Firewood/Charcoal			
19. Other (Specify)			
20. Other (specify)			

I. HOUSEHOLD FOOD AND NUTRITION SECURITY

I.1 HH Food Security

	Two years ago	Last year
1.1 Did the HH harvest take you through two years ago and last year? 1) Yes 2) No		
1.2 When did you run out of your own cultivated food two years ago and last year? (Allow for multiple choice) 1).January and February 5) September and October 2) March and April 6) November and December 3) May and June 7) Do not know 4) July and August		
1.3 Did the HH buy food two years ago and last year? 1) Yes 2) No		
1.4 When did you buy the food two years ago and last year? (Allow for multiple choice) 1).January and February 5) September and October 2) March and April 6) November and December 3) May and June 7) Do not know 4) July and August		
1.5 How did you obtain money to buy the food two years ago and last year? (Allow for multiple choice) 1) Income from salaried work 2) Sale of cash crops 3) Sale of food crops 4) Sale of animals 5) Remittances from relatives 6) Petty trading 7) Credit (cash or in-kind) 8) Other (specify)		

1.6 Do you expect to experience food shortage in your household this year? 1)Yes 2) No

1.7 Why or why not? (Please probe for causes)

.....

.....

1.8 Which year within the past 5 years will you regard as the most difficult in terms of food availability in the household?

1) 5 years ago 2) 4 years ago 3) 3 years ago 4) 2 years ago 5) Last year

1.9 Why?

I.2: Household Dietary Diversity (HDDS) [Using mainly local foods]

Please describe the foods (meals and snacks) that you ate or drank yesterday during the day and night, whether at home or outside the home. Start with the first food or drink eaten in the morning. *[Please refer to list of foods attached]*

	Questions	Coding [1) Yes, 2) No]
2.1	Any bread, porridge, , TZ, Banku, Kenkey, Noodles, biscuits, Nyeleng, pancake, cus cus, mbahal, chackry, or any other foods made from millet, sorghum, maize, rice, wheat, findi or <i>[any other locally available grain]</i> ?	A [....]
2.2	Any yams, cassava, konkonte, potatoes, Cocoyam, porridge, gari, ebeh, plasas soup, or any other foods made from roots or tubers?	B [.....]
2.3	Any vegetables; eg Bera, Ayoyo, Kontomere, Okro, cabbage, moringa leaves, green-green, mboroch, armranthus, sorrel, baobab leaves etc	C [...]
2.4	Any fruits? E.g. Tama (shea), Orange, Mango, bananas, ga-a, ara, kaba, tamarin, guava, tomborong, baobab, paw paw, Dimbu etc	D [...]
2.5	Any beef, pork, sheep/lamb, goat, rabbit, wild game, chicken, duck, or other birds, liver, kidney, heart, or other organ meats?	E [.....]
2.6	Any eggs? Chicken, guinea fowl, ducks, turkey, queles	F [.....]
2.7	Any fresh or dried fish or shellfish? Tilapia, bonga, cat fish, lady fish, barracuda, sea snail	G [.....]
2.8	Any foods made from beans and/or g'nuts, eg. "Red-red" etc.? Akra, domoda, gine job, cooked beans+cassava+fried fish, cooked beans+bread	H [....]
2.9	Any cheese, yogurt, milk or other milk products? Fresh milk, fermented milk, cow oil,	I [...]
2.10	Any foods made with oil, fat, or butter? Meat stew, fish stew, jollof rice, pancake, fishcake, chackry	J [.....]
2.11	Any sugar or honey? Fresh honey, sugar candy	K [...]
2.12	Any other foods, such as condiments, dawadawa, coffee, tea. Sobolo, mbormbor, kinkiliba, wonjo, tamarin, boabab?	L [.....]
Total	Sum (A + B + C + D + E + F + G + H + I + J + K + L)

J. USE OF NATURAL RESOURCES

J.1 Availability and Use of Household Lands

What area of land is owned/used by: (Please estimate in acres/hectares)	1.1 Cultivated land (state area in acres/hectares)		1.2 Fallow land (state area in acres/hectares)		1.3 Virgin land (never cultivated) (state area in acres/hectares)
	Owned	Not owned	Owned	Not owned but accessible	Owned
Household head					
Male members of the HH (excluding HHH)					
Female members of HH (excluding HHH)					

1.4 Can the HH get more land for farming purposes within the community? (1) Yes (2) No

1.5 If yes, how?

1) Inheritance; 2) Leased; 3) Rented; 4) Borrowed (Free); 5) Share cropping; 6) Others (specify)

.....

1.6 If no, why? (Please probe for reasons)

.....

1.7 Under what conditions will you give part of your land to somebody else to farm?

.....

1.8 What type of crops are allowed to be grown on the land (given to others to farm)? 1) Arable crops 2) Annual cash crops (e.g. cotton) 3) Tree crops 4) Other (Specify)

.....

J.2 Women and youth access to the use and ownership of land and trees

Level/rating	2.1. Women's ownership of rainfed land	2.2 Women's access to use of rainfed land	2.3 Women's ownership of irrigated land	2.4 Women's access to use of irrigated land	2.5 Women's ownership of (semi-wild) economic trees (shea, dawadawa, baobab, tamarin, tombrong, kaba, talo, neto, rahlm palm etc)	2.6 Women's access to use of economic trees (shea, dawadawa, neto, baobab, tamarin, kaba, talo etc.)	2.7 Women's access to land for exotic economic trees (e.g. mango, cashew, oranges, paw paw, guava, lime, banana, avocado pear, jack fruit etc.)	2.8 Women's access to land for woodlots (teak, acacia, gymaliana, sesbania, African mahogany, rose wood, eculyptus etc.)
High								
Moderate								
Low								
None (no access)								
Not applicable*								

*Applies to situations where the resource does not exist in the community.

2.9 Which category of **women** can own land in your community?

Level/Rating	2.10 Youth ownership of rainfed land	2.11 Youth access to use of rainfed land	2.12 Youth ownership of irrigated land	2.13 Youth access to use of irrigated land	2.14 Youth ownership of (semi-wild) economic trees (shea, dawadawa etc)	2.15 Youth access to use of economic trees (shea, dawadawa etc.)	2.16 Youth access to land for exotic economic trees (e.g. mango, cashew etc.)	2.17 Youth access to land for woodlots (teak, acacia etc.)
High								
Moderate								
Low								
None (no access)								
Not applicable*								

*Applies to situations where the resource does not exist in the community.

2.18 Which category of the **youth** can own land in your community?

Continuous use of land by Women and Youth

	2.19 Under normal circumstances, how long will you being a woman be allowed to continue to use land for: (If indefinitely put 99)	2.20 Under normal circumstances, how long will a youth be allowed to continue to use land for: (If indefinitely put 99)
Rainfed farming		
Irrigated farming		
Exotic economic trees (mango, cashew etc)		
Woodlots		

J.3 Women and Youth's access to inorganic and organic fertilizers, Weedicides, and Insecticides

Level/Rating	3.1 Women's access to inorganic fertilizers	3.2 Women's access to organic fertilizers (FYM/Compost)	3.3 Women's access to weedicides	3.4. Women's access to insecticides	3.5 Women's access to bio-weedicides and bio-insecticides
High					
Moderate					
Low					
None (no access)					

	3.6 Access to inorganic fertilizers by youth	3.7 Access to organic fertilizers by youth (FYM and compost)	3.8 Access to weedicides by youth	3.9 Access to insecticides by youth	3.10 Access to bio-weedicides and bio-insecticides by youth
High					
Moderate					
Low					
None (no access)					

J.4 Give scores to the following inputs in terms of importance (see below the table) and state why

Input	Score	Reason for score
4.1 Inorganic fertilizers		
4.2 Organic fertilizers		
4.3 Weedicides		
4.4 Insecticides		
4.5 Bio-weedicides		
4.6 Bio-insecticides		

Score: 1) Very important 2) Important 3) Somehow important 4) Not important 5) Not necessary

K. GENERAL CHANGES IN LAND USE OVER TIME

K.1. Which of these items were known, produced, used and/or available in the area 10, 30 and 50 years ago but are no longer seen.

1.0 Item	1.1 About 10 years ago	1.2 About 30 years ago	1.3 About 50 years ago	1.4 What are the reasons for their disappearance?	1.5 Is the situation: 1. Getting better 2. Same 3. Getting worse
1. Indigenous crops					
2. Introduced crops					
3. Indigenous Trees					
4. Introduced trees					
5. Shrubs					
6. Indigenous livestock					
7. Introduced (exotic) livestock					
8. Wildlife					
9. Water bodies/wetlands					
10. Irrigated agriculture					
11. Farming systems (production practices)					

K.2. Which of these items are now available but were not known in the area in the past 10, 30 and 50 years ago?

2.0 Item	2.1 Now available but not known in the past (i.e introduced crops, trees etc.)	2.2 What are the reasons for the appearance of these crops/trees/shrubs/livestock/wildlife?
1. Indigenous crops		
2. Introduced crops		
3. Indigenous Trees		
4. Introduced tress		
5. Shrubs		
6. Indigenous livestock		
7. Introduced (exotic) livestock		
8. Wildlife		
9. Water bodies/wetlands		
10. Irrigated agriculture		
11. Farming systems (production practices)		

K.3 Description of land use changes/transition over time:

3.0 What was on various lands in past years	3.1 50 years ago	3.2 30 years ago	3.3 10 years ago	3.4 5 years ago
Compound farmlands				
Bush farmlands				
Other lands used before				

1. Cultivated land 2) Irregular cultivated land 3) Grazing land/grassland 4) Dams/dugouts 5) Bareground 6) Natural forest/woodland
 7) Open woodland (shrubs and scattered trees) 8) Cultivated trees 9) Other (Specify)

L. NATURAL RESOURCES DEGRADATION

Degraded Lands and Soils

1.1 What area of your land is so degraded that it cannot be used for farming? (acres/hectares)

Rank **FIVE** main causes of land degradation (including soil, forest/grassland degradation) in your community.

1.2 Main cause (Choose from below - Codes)	1.3 Rank (1 to 5 Most severe to least severe)	1.4 What should be done to tackle the problem?

Codes: 1) Bush burning 2) Deforestation/Charcoal making 3) Illegal/small scale mining 4) Sand winning 5) Continuous cropping 6) Improper fertilizer use 7) Wrong tillage (use of heavy machinery) 8) Wrong disposal of plastic waste 9) Rapid urbanization 10) Wrong use of agrochemicals (atrazine based weedicides) (land and fishing) 11) Invasive species 12) Other (specify).

What methods have you used to restore degraded lands?

1.5 Method (Codes A)	1.6 From whom did you acquire the knowledge (Codes B)	1.7 Level of success (1= very successful, 5=not successful)	1.8 Remarks on method (positive and/or negative comments on method)

Codes A (for 1.5): 1. Natural regeneration 2. Fallow 3. Agroforestry 4. Organic matter or soil amendments 5. Other (specify)

Codes (for 1.6): 1) Traditional 2) Ministry 3) NGO personnel 4) Other farmers 5) Students/School children 6) Other (specify)

1.9 What change in production did you realize after the land restoration? 1) Increase 2) No change 3) Decrease

M. WEALTH (POVERTY) STATUS

1.1 Please rank your household in terms of wealth status.

1. Very wealthy (rich) 2. Wealthy (rich) 3. Averagely wealthy 4.. Poor
5. Very poor

1.2 Justify your answer

Give **FIVE** main indicators of poverty in this community? (Rank them from 1 to 5, the best indicator being 1)

1.3 Indicator of poverty	1.4 Rank (1 to 5 Most severe to least severe)

1.5 About what percentage (proportion) of the people in this community will you consider as:

- (1) Very rich%
- (2) Rich %
- (3) Average %
- (4) Poor %
- (5) Very poor %

Use the following codes to answer questions 1.6, 1.7, 1.8, and 1.9 (Choose five or less in each case)

1. Arable crop farming 2. Tree crop farming 3. Livestock farming 4. Aquaculture (fish farming) 5. Fishing (fish & sea foods) 6. Fish mongering
7. Produce marketing (Crop) 8. Livestock marketing (incl. produce) 9. Local drink brewing (e.g. pito in Ghana) 10. Malt processing 11. Tree produce processing
(e.g. shea, dawadawa, boabab etc.) 12. Petty trading/food vending 13. Salaried worker 14. Tradesman (Bricklayer, carpenter, tailor etc.) 15. Artisan (basket weaver,
potter etc.) 16. Chiefs 17. Landowners 18. Butchers 19. The aged 20. Others (specify)

1.6 Who or which groups of people (in terms of occupation) can be considered **wealthy** among the **men** in this community?

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1.7 Who or which groups of people (in terms of occupation) can be considered **wealthy** among the **women** in this community? (Use Codes of 1.6)

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1.8 Who or which groups of people (in terms of occupation) can be considered **very poor** among the **men** in this community?

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1.9 Who or which groups of people (in terms of occupation) can be considered **very poor** among the **women** in this community?

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N. AGROECOLOGICAL/CLIMATE SMART/SUSTAINABLE LAND MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

N.1 Knowledge, Use and Perceptions of Effectiveness of agroecological/CS/SLM Practices

	CS/SLM Practices	1.1. Does farmer know technology? 1) Yes 2) No	1.2 Source of Information (Codes A)	1.3 Use during 2022 season 1) Yes 2) No	1.4 Use during past 5 years 1)Yes 2) No	1.5 Area of farm under this technique in 2022 (acres/hectares)	1.6 Reasons for never used or stopped using (Codes B)	1.7 Factors that determine adoption (Codes C)	1.8 Who decides? (Codes D)	1.9 Effectiveness (Codes E)
1	Mulching									
2	Soil bunds									
3	Crop residues management									
4	Cover cropping									
5	Improved water management									
6	Early maturing /drought resistant varieties									
7	Minimum/No tillage									
8	Rainwater harvesting (through bunds, zai etc)									
9	Zai									
10	Grass(Vertiver) Strips									
11	Green manure e.g. Mucuna									

12	Compost									
13	Improved grazing									
14	Crop rotation									
15	Fallow									
16	Farmyard manure									
17	Burying of weeds									
18	Intercropping with grain legumes									
19	Integrated crop-livestock mgt.									
20	Stone bunds/terracing									
22	Contour planting									
23	Basins									
24	Woodlots									
25	Agroforestry (trees in farm)									
26	Lime (Ash)									
27	Ground water use (with pumps) for dry season farming									
28	Drip Irrigation									
29	Biochar									
30	Weather forecasting									
31	Early warning systems									
32	Climate-risk insurance									
33	Other (specify)									
34	Other (specify)									

Codes A: 1) Ministry 2) Research institution (e.g. SARI, UDS, ISRA, NSS etc. 3) NGO 4) Other farmer(s) 5) Radio 6) Local chief(s) or opinion leader 7) Students/School children 8) Other (Specify)

Codes B: 1) Land is fertile 2) High cost 3) Very risky 4) Non-availability of requisite inputs locally 5) More labour required 6) Small land holdings 7) Low expected benefits 8) “Spoils the soil” 9) Lack of knowledge 10) Unclear land rights ownership 11) Time taken to realize benefits too long 12) Other (Specify)

Codes C: 1) Land is infertile 2) Low cost of technology 3) Low risk 4) Availability of inputs 5) Low labour 6) High expected benefits 7) Improves the soil 8) Technically capable 9) Secure land tenure 10) Other (Specify)

Codes D: 1) Household Head 2) Husband only 3) Wife only 4) Husband and wife 5) Youth only 6) Other (specify)

Codes E: 1) Highly effective 2) Effective 3) Ineffective (no change) 4) Highly ineffective

1.10 Which of the agroecological/CS/SLM practices listed above are community-based?

1.11 Which persons in the community can you describe as a “agroecology champions” (good practitioners of agroecology, climate smart and sustainable land management). (Give specific names or groups).
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N.2 SPECIFIC AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES

2.1 Management of seeds and breeds (One choice please)

- 1) All seeds and/or animal genetic resources (e.g., chicks, young animals, semen) are purchased from the market.
- 2) More than 80% of seeds/ animal genetic resources are purchased from the market.
- 3) About half of the seeds are self-produced or exchanged, the other half is purchased from the market. About half of the breeding is done with neighbouring farms.
- 4) The majority of seeds/animal genetic resources are self-produced or exchanged. Some specific seeds are purchased from the market.
- 5) All seeds/animal genetic resources are self-produced, exchanged with other farmers or managed collectively, ensuring enough renewal and diversity.

2.2 Crop-livestock-aquaculture integration (One choice please)

- 1) **No integration:** animals, including fish are fed with purchased feed and their manure is not used for soil fertility; no animals in the agroecosystem.
- 2) **Low integration:** animals are mostly fed with purchased feed, their manure is used as fertiliser.
- 3) **Medium integration:** animals are mostly fed with feed produced on the farm and/or grazing, their manure is used as fertiliser.
- 4) **High integration:** animals are mostly fed with feed produced on the farm, crop residues and by-products and/or grazing, their manure is used as fertiliser and they provide at least one service (e.g. traction)
- 5) **Complete integration:** animals are exclusively fed with feed produced on the farm, crop residues and by-products and/or grazing, all their manure is recycled as fertiliser and they provide more than one service (food, products, traction, etc.)

2.3 Soil-plant system management (One choice please)

- 1) **Soil is bare after harvest. No intercropping. No crop rotations** (or rotational grazing systems). Heavy soil disturbance (biological, chemicals or machines).
- 2) **Less than 20% of the arable land is covered with residues or cover crops.** More than 80% of the crops are produced in mono and continuous cropping (or no rotational grazing).
- 3) **50% of soil is covered with residues or cover crops.** Some crops are rotated or intercropped (or some rotational grazing is carried out).
- 4) **More than 80% of the soil is covered with residues or cover crops.** Crops are rotated regularly or intercropped (or rotational grazing is systematic). Soil disturbance is minimized.
- 5) **All the soil is covered with residues or cover crops.** Crops are rotated regularly, and intercropping is common (or rotational grazing is systematic). Little or no soil disturbance.

2.4 Management of biomass and nutrients (One choice please)

- 1) Residues and by-products are not recycled (e.g., left for decomposition or burnt). Large amounts of waste are discharged or burnt.
- 2) A small part of the residues and by-products is recycled (e.g. crop residues as animal feed, use of manure as fertiliser, production of compost from manure and household waste, green manure). Waste is discharged or burnt.
- 3) More than half of the residues and by-products is recycled. Some waste is discharged or burnt.
- 4) Most of the residues and by-products are recycled. Only a little waste is discharged or burnt.
- 5) All the residues and by-products are recycled. No waste is discharged or burnt.

N.3 Use of Agro-Wastes

What use is made of the following agro-wastes?

Agro-wastes	3.1 Incorporate into the soil/mulch 1) Yes 2) No	3.2 Sale 1) Yes 2) No	3.3 livestock feed/bedding 1) Yes 2) No	3.4 Use as source of fuel (energy) 1) Yes 2) No	3.5 Composting 1) Yes 2) No	3.6 Use as building material 1) Yes 2) No	3.7 Other (specify)
Cereals (stovers not stowers)							
Legumes							
Grasses							
Animal manure (cow dung, chicken manure etc)							
Wastes from abattoirs							
Kitchen wastes							
Other wastes (specify)							

What quantities are generated per acre/hectare, period available, and what processing carried out?

Agro-wastes	3.8 Quantity generated per acre/hectare (% of harvest gathered as waste)	3.9 Period available (months) (1 – 12)	3.10 What processing carried out?	3.11 Challenges faced
Cereals (stovers)				
Legumes				
Grasses				
Forest/trees residues (e.g. leaves)				
Animal manure (cow dung, chicken manure etc)				
Wastes from abattoirs				
Kitchen wastes				
Other wastes (specify)				

O. YIELDS CHANGE OVER TIME

1.1 How have crop yields generally changed on your farms in the past 5 years?

- 1) Increased; 2) No change 3) Decreased

1.2 If the crop yields have increased or decreased, in your opinion, what are the 5 main reasons responsible for this?

	A	B		C	D
	Reasons for increase	Rank (1-5; 1 is the most important)		Reasons for decrease	Rank (1-5; 1 the most important)
1)	Planting improved varieties		1)	Planting local varieties	
2)	No/control pests and diseases		2)	Pests and diseases	
3)	Reliable rainfall		3)	Unreliable rainfall	
4)	Fertile soils		4)	Poor soil fertility	
5)	Good land management		5)	Soil erosion	
6)	Good crop management		6)	Weeds	
7)	Uses enough fertilizer/manure		7)	Do not use / uses less inputs	
8)	No labour constraints		8)	Labour constraints	
9)	Available finance		9)	Financial constraints	

P. CLIMATE CHANGE

1.1 Have you ever experienced the following losses due to climatic and social forces? How many times in last 10 years?

	1) Yes 2) No	How many times in 10 years
A. Complete or near-complete crop loss due to drought (at least 50% loss)		
B. Complete or near-complete crop loss due to causes other than drought – e.g. flood, hail, locust, disease, fire etc.		
C. Complete or near-complete crop loss due to theft, conflicts (over 50% loss)		
D. Complete or near-complete herd loss - specify the cause: theft, wildlife predators, drought, disease, etc. (Over 50% loss),		

1.2 Do you think climate has changed over time? **1)** Yes **2)** No

1.3 What evidences can you cite or what happened with climate change?

Evidences of climate change/happenings	Response 1. Yes 2. No	Rank 1 to 5, those that give the greatest evidence of climate change (1 - the greatest evidence)
Temperature increased		
Temperature decreased		
Rainfall decreased		
Droughts have increased		
Floods have increased		
Increase in vegetative cover		
Decrease in vegetative cover		
Change of rainfall patterns		
Change in cropping season		
Change in type of crops grown		
Rivers have dried		
Swamps have dried		
New insects emerged		
Increase in crop species (increase in biodiversity)		
Other (specify) ..		

1.4 In your opinion what are the **best five** adaptation/mitigation measures against climate change related disasters? [Rank from 1 (best) to 5 (least)]

Climate adaptation/Mitigation measures	Rank (1 – best)
Crop diversification/mixed cropping	
Planting of trees/windbreaks (woodlots)	
Agroforestry	
Crop-livestock integration	
Early warning systems	
Drought resistant crop varieties	
Pest and disease resistant crop varieties	
Irrigated agriculture	
Climate-risk insurance	
Other (specify)	
Other (Specify)	

Q. ANTI-ENVIRONMENT PRACTICES

Give reasons for these practices in your community and suggest what ways to reduce their prevalence.

Practice	1.1 Which categories of persons undertake these practices? Code A	1.2 Reasons for the practices Code B	1.3 What should be done to reduce prevalence? Code C	1.4 Are there any community (cultural) prohibitions/taboos with respect to the practice. 1) Yes 2) No	1.5 Are there any by-laws against to engagement in these practices 1) Yes 2) No
1) Deforestation (Illegal logging/charcoal production and firewood cutting)					
2) Bush burning (fires)					
3) Burning of farm residues					
4) Use of agrochemical in farms (especially weedicides)					
5) Use of agrochemical in water bodies					
6) Illegal/small scale mining					
7) Sand minning /stone quarrying					
8) Others (Specify)					

Multiple answers (up to three) are allowed) for A, B and C

Code A: 1) Men 2) Women 3) Youth 4) Migrants 5) Nomads (herders) 6) Farmers 7) Hunters 8) Charcoal producers 9) Wood loggers 10) Road contractors 11) Smokers 12) Foreigners 13) Other (Specify)

Code B: 1) cultivation of food crops 2) tree crop plantations (e.g. cashew) 3) charcoal/firewood production 4) Construction of roads 5) bushmeat 6) because of lack of labour

Code C: 1) Legislation (district/community level bye-laws) with strict enforcement 2) Education and sensitization 3) Enforcement of taboos 4) Provision of alternative livelihood opportunities 5) Formation of volunteer groups (e.g. volunteer fire groups) 6) Other (specify)

R. RESOURCE USE-BASED CONFLICTS

1.1 Have you been involved in any conflict over use of common resources (farmland, water, grassland, economic trees etc.)? 1) Yes 2) No

1.2 If yes, please explain the circumstances and the consequences

1.3 How many times in the last three years?

1.4 If no, is there a possibility of common resources use conflict in the future? 1) Yes 2) No.

1.5 Are you aware of resource conflict areas in the district? 1) Yes 2) No. If yes, name the areas.

1.6 Please explain the nature of the conflict (if you can)

1.7 How was the conflict resolved?

1.8 In your opinion what is the best way to **avoid** natural resource use conflicts?

1.9 In your opinion what is the best way to **resolve** natural resource use conflicts when they occur?

R. DIGITAL TOOLS

1.1 Which of these digital tools are used by men, women and the youth in the households?

Tool	Men – 1) Yes 2) No	Women 1) Yes 2) No	Youth 1) Yes 2) No
Non-smart phones			
Radio (access to radio eg., phones)			
Television (TV)			
Smart phone (Voice)			
Smart phone (Voice and SMS)			
Smart phone (Voice, SMS and Whatsapp)			
Smart phone (Voice, SMS, Whatsapp +)			
Computer (No email)			
Computer (email)			
Other (specify)			
None			

1.2 Have you used a digital tool to support your agricultural production, marketing, etc? 1) Yes 2) No

1.3 If yes explain how it was used?

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1.4 If no, why have you not used any?

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1.5 For those who are using digital tools, state constraints faced?

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